

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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IMPLEMENTATION OF CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINES FOR
HEPATITIS C INFECTION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) is the most common chronic blood-borne liver infection affecting an estimated 3-5 million Americans annually. It is a leading cause of end-stage liver disease, hepatocellular carcinoma, and liver transplant. HCV is transmitted sexually, through needlestick injuries, needle sharing, mother-to-child transmission, blood transfusions, and during tattooing or piercings. The number of people with Acute HCV tripled between 2011-2016 due to an increase in IV drug use associated with the opioid epidemic. Timely screening and treatment of HCV infection can prevent disease transmissions, reducing the chances for liver diseases and its complications. Evidence-based practice (EBP) guidelines can help providers remain up-to-date with new recommendations leading them to manage and treat HCV effectively. The purpose of this DNP project was to develop, implement, and evaluate EBP guidelines for screening and treatment of patients at risk for HCV infection in an outpatient Gastroenterology clinic without an established clinical practice guideline. A tailored HCV screening and treatment protocol was developed, piloted, and evaluated at the clinical practice site by using the Plan Do Study Act (PDSA) cycle framework. Data was collected and trended biweekly for 12 weeks. The results were analyzed using the QI Macros. Overall, at the end of project implementation, the rates of HCV screening increased from an average of 50% to 71%, with the promise of an average of more than 80% beyond week 12. The PDSA model was effective in driving a new evidence-based practice changes in

implementing new clinical practice guidelines, leading to increased screening, diagnostics, and treatment of HCV positive patients. Future recommendations for clinicians include focusing on staff, patient, and family education to raise awareness of HCV infection, assisting patients in navigating insurance and social resources, and encouraging patients to make a follow-up appointment who refuse HCV screening (patients with risk factors).

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BACKGROUND

Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) infection is considered as the most common chronic blood-borne infection in the United States (U.S.), affects three to five million Americans, and is a leading cause of end-stage liver disease and hepatocellular carcinoma, although most patients with HCV infection remain asymptomatic, making early purposeful screening difficult (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2019; Jacobson, Lim, & Fried, 2017; Squires & Balistreri, 2017; Udompap, Mannalithara, Heo, Kim, & Kim, 2016; Younossi et al., 2016). Udompap et al. (2016) stated that the actual number of HCV cases is even higher, as many individuals are unaware of their status. In the U.S., it is estimated that baby boomers account for three-fourths of HCV infections (Dieterich, 2015; Younossi et al., 2016). Baby boomers, defined as the generation born between 1946 and 1964, are identified in the literature as a high risk for contracting HCV (CDC, 2019; Kasting et al., 2018; Moore, Gauri, & Koru-Sengul, 2018; World Health Organization [WHO], 2019).

The cause for baby boomers' high risk for HCV infection is not well understood. However, it is presumed those baby boomers could have acquired the virus through contaminated medical equipment or procedures during the 1960s through 1980s when universal precautions and infection control procedures were not yet adopted (CDC, 2019; WHO, 2019). Reducing the HCV burden in the U.S. requires healthcare providers to regularly screen and treat patients who are at risk for infection (CDC, 2019a; Chaatwal et al., 2016; Younossi et al., 2016).

New HCV therapies have shown a better cure rate than traditional therapies (Alleman, 2017; CDC, 2019b). Despite this increased rate, the literature states screening,

initiation, and completion of treatment present complex barriers to successful screening and treatment (CDC, 2018; Chou, Cottrell, Wasson, Rahman, & Guise, 2013; Grebely, Oser, Taylor, & Dore, 2013; Shehata, Austin, Ha, & Timmerman, 2018; Sublette, Smith, George, McCaffery, & Douglas, 2015). Although screening and treatment are widely discussed in the literature, only a handful of studies specifically discuss the impact of provider compliance and adherence to standard guidelines of screening and treatment on patient treatment uptake and adherence (Kasting et al., 2018; Trinh & Turner, 2018). Standard evidence-based practice (EBP) guidelines can help providers remain up-to-date with new recommendations, lead them in effective decision-making in management and treatment of HCV, and prevent related complications such as liver cirrhosis, failure, and cancer (CDC, 2018; Chung et al., 2018; Dieterich et al., 2019; Guss, Sherigar, Rosen, & Mohanty, 2018). Hence, it is essential for healthcare providers to be extensively trained in the diagnosis and treatment of HCV and to follow up-to-date screening and treatment guidelines and protocols for best and optimal patient care (Dieterich et al., 2019; Kasting et al., 2018; Southern et al., 2014).

HCV Health Implications

As it is a blood-borne disease, HCV infection can be transmitted sexually, through needlestick injuries in health care settings, by sharing needles and syringes for intravenous drug (IV) use, from mother to child in utero, and during tattooing or piercings (American Association for the Study of Liver Disease [AASLD], 2018; CDC, 2018; Squires & Balistreri, 2017; WHO, 2019). The infection's effects range from mild to life-threatening negative health sequelae, such as liver cancer or death (CDC, 2018). Liver diseases associated with this infection have been identified as the primary cause of

liver transplants in the U.S. (Chou et al., 2013). The CDC (2018) recently reported an estimated 2,967 cases of acute HCV infection in 42 U.S. states. Untreated HCV infection can lead to other health complications, such as heart problems, muscle and joint pains, kidney dysfunction, depression, eventually negatively affecting the overall quality of life (CDC, 2019a; Gardenier & Olson, 2019; Moore et al., 2019; Younossi et al., 2016). The CDC (2019b) states that effective screening and treatment can prevent about 120,000 HCV-related deaths and annually save the nation between \$1.5 and \$7.5 billion.

Sustained viral response (SVR) is a measure of HCV treatment success achieved when the virus is not detected in the bloodstream for 12 weeks during and after completion of treatment (Dieterich et al., 2019; Terrault & Hassanein, 2016). Recently approved pan-genotypic (appropriate for all genotypes) HCV therapies currently show a 95% to 97% SVR rate compared to traditional therapies which have an SVR rate of 15% to 20% (Alleman, 2017; CDC, 2019b; Lebovics, Torres, & Porter, 2017; Terrault & Hassanein, 2016; Younossi et al., 2016). Sofosbuvir/Velpatasvir (Epclusa), Sofosbuvir (Sovaldi), and Glecaprevir/Pibrentasvir (Mavyret) are pan-genotypic HCV therapies newly approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA). These therapies are well tolerated and require only eight to twelve weeks of treatment (Dieterich et al., 2019; Guss et al., 2018). Hence, timely screening and treatment of HCV infection can prevent transmissions, which reduces the chance of liver disease and its complications (Dieterich et al., 2019).

Patient Considerations

The literature presents, from the patients' lens, common barriers to HCV treatment uptake and adherence which may affect the success of screening and treatment

(Dieterich et al., 2019; Grebely et al., 2013; Shehata et al., 2018; Southern et al., 2014). These barriers include potential negative stigma attached with having a diagnosis of HCV and IV drug use, providers' inconsistency with treatment approaches, and language differences (Shehata et al., 2018; Sublette, Smith, George, McCaffery, & Douglas, 2017; Younossi et al., 2016). Similarly, a qualitative study, conducted by Sublette et al. (2015), found provider-patient communication, limitations of the healthcare system as a whole, and social stigma as particular barriers to patients' treatment adherence. The common barriers discussed by Grebely et al. (2013) coincide with similar findings regarding financial issues, lack of transportation, personal health insurance, poverty, social stigma, incarceration, and inadequate access to care (Lynch & Wu, 2016; Younossi et al., 2016). In contrast, compared to other studies, Grebely et al. (2013) pointed out that patients' lack of knowledge about HCV infection was one of the major barriers to accessing care. Likewise, a systematic literature review conducted by Shehata et al. (2018) showed societal stigma and discrimination were additional barriers.

Health Care Provider Role

Providers play a vital role in the screening and treatment of HCV and can help reduce disease transmission, mortality, and morbidity (Lebovics et al., 2017; Shehata et al., 2018). Providers' current knowledge of HCV screening and treatment recommendations can enhance their ability to better screen and treat their patients (Grebely et al., 2013; Shehata et al., 2018). Evidence-based clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) can be used as a guidance tool to screen and treat for infection (Dieterich, 2015; Dieterich et al., 2019; Guss et al., 2018). Multiple researchers suggest that most HCV-infected patients are not aware of their status (Lebovics et al., 2017; Shehata et al., 2018;

Udompap et al., 2016; Younossi et al., 2016). Hence, providers, by screening patients during their first visit, can identify those at risk for infection and treat them if they are eligible (Shehata et al., 2018). Appropriate screening can lead to proper evaluation and treatment of individuals chronically infected with HCV, preventing adverse health sequelae (Chou et al., 2013; Dieterich et al., 2019; Joshi, 2014; Younossi et al., 2016). The literature discusses patients' decision to start treatment, maintain, and complete their treatment as dependent on the quality of communication between patient and provider. The research identified this factor as an important aspect of maintaining patients' adherence to treatment (Grebely et al., 2013; Shehata et al., 2018; Sublette et al., 2015; Sublette et al., 2017). Therefore, improved quality of care can improve patients' quality of life by preventing complications such as liver failure and cancer (CDC, 2018; Chou et al., 2013).

HCV Screening and Treatment Guidelines

The CDC, U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF), the American Gastroenterology Association (AGA), and the AASLD currently recommend HCV screening in individuals born between 1945 and 1965, with at least one risk factor, such as history of IV drug use, received blood or organs before July 1992, born to an HCV-positive mother, positive human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection, history of tattooing and body piercing, and currently or previously incarcerated persons (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC, 2019b; Moyer, 2013; WHO, 2019). Similarly, the USPSTF, AGA, and AASLD recommend one-time HCV infection testing for people born between 1945 and 1965 (Moyer, 2013). In 2013, the AGA developed a clinical decision-making pathway consisting of 13 steps. The first step is an initial evaluation of people born

between 1945 and 1965 who have never been tested for HCV infection (AGA, 2019). The second and third steps focus on HCV screening for people with identified high-risk factors such as a history of blood transfusion before 1992 or IV drug use (AGA, 2019). Steps four through thirteen involve comprehensive screening and treatment of HCV-positive individuals with antiviral therapy followed by post-treatment care (AGA, 2019). Additionally, the newly updated guidelines recommend screening all pregnant women for HCV infection after a study found an increase in the number of HCV-infected women giving birth between 2011 and 2014 (AASLD, 2018; WHO, 2019). The Society for Maternal-Fetal Medicine aligned its recommendations with those of the WHO regarding screening childbearing women who could also be at risk for HCV (Hughes, Page, & Kuller, 2017).

The WHO describes HCV infection as a public threat and stated a goal of eliminating it by 2030 by reducing new viral cases to 90% and decreasing deaths associated with viral hepatitis by 65% with recently approved pan-genotypic and simplified treatment (Dieterich et al., 2019; WHO, 2019). Likewise, the Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS) recently released a campaign, *National Viral Hepatitis Action Plan, 2017-2020*, with the goal of reducing health disparities in viral hepatitis by focusing on prevention, care, and treatment, and urging the nation to work together to eliminate these infections (DHHS, 2019). There is a call for providers to screen patients at risk for HCV infection and treat them when appropriate to prevent an increase in infection further and reduce complications and deaths (CDC, 2019a; DHHS, 2019; WHO, 2019). Evidence-based CPGs can help clinicians effectively manage and

treat their patients with HCV infection to improve health outcomes (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC, 2019b; Dieterich et al., 2019).

Problem Statement

The project site was an outpatient gastroenterology (GI) clinic with two providers in Orange County, California. The site served patients with gastrointestinal and liver diseases, such as hepatitis B (HBV) and HCV. This includes patients at risk for infection, such as baby boomers and patients with high-risk behaviors like a history of IV drug use. This clinic saw a high volume of patients; 45 to 48 patients between two providers in half a day. The CPGs are lengthy, complex, and difficult to navigate during daily patient care, as there was no easy access to computers for providers at this site. The facility used a paper charting system. There was a lack of HCV screening and treatment guidelines in place, preventing patients from receiving care in a systematic and evidence-based manner. Hence, upon assessment, this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) student identified a need for organized, easy-to-follow, accessible protocols to improve care for HCV patients in this clinic. Additionally, a standardized protocol would improve communication between providers and staff, enhancing consistency of care for patients and improving their overall health outcomes.

Purpose Statement

Despite serving a population at risk for or identified as HCV-positive, the setting had no standardized CPGs for screening and treatment. Therefore, the purpose of this DNP project was to develop, implement, and evaluate EBP guidelines for screening and treatment for patients at risk of or with HCV infection at this outpatient GI clinic.

Supporting Framework

Plan, Do, Study, Act

The Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) model is a well-structured and straightforward model that can help effect positive change in a clinical setting (Crowfoot & Prasad, 2017). The PDSA cycle is commonly used in healthcare settings to improve care practices and overall quality of care and is presented in Figure 1. The PDSA cycle is also widely known as the Deming Cycle. Initially, the PDSA cycle came from the technology industry in Tokyo, Japan, and was adapted from the work of Walter Shewhart in the 1920s (Taylor et al., 2014). Shewhart introduced the concept of the plan, do, and see, and Deming, a statistician, modified the cycle into what is currently known as the four stages of PDSA (Cantiello, Kitsantas, Moncada, & Abdul, 2016). The PDSA method follows a four-stage cycle beginning with “plan” and ending with “action” following a quality improvement learning approach to implement new processes or improve current ones. In the “plan” stage, a change aimed at improvement is identified. The “do” stage involves testing the planned change, leading to the “study” stage of examining the outcomes of the change (Crowfoot & Prasad, 2017). In the “act” stage, adaptations are identified to inform whether a new cycle is necessary (Crowfoot & Prasad, 2017). In this DNP project, the PDSA cycle was used to implement current EBP guidelines for the screening and treatment of HCV infections.

Plan. During the first stage of PDSA, the team identifies the area of concern or need for improvement and establishes objectives (Provost & Murray, 2011). The project team consisted of the medical doctor/medical director (MD), nurse practitioner/team lead (TL), receptionist, appointment scheduler, medical assistants, instructional technology

(IT) specialist, and financial services personnel. The first stage of this proposed project included a review of the literature on EBP guidelines for HCV screening and treatment protocols, specifically in common-based small clinic settings. Current practice guidelines and protocols, as well as supporting resources, were assessed. Through preliminary planning meetings, the TL educated the team on best practices and evidence-based guidelines for HCV screening. The TL sought input on adapting practices for the clinic and patients. The TL facilitated discussion regarding the implementation of a new protocol. The potential timelines for this project were outlined to track the project's progress.

Do. Changes are implemented during the second stage (Crowfoot & Prasad, 2017). The team received education on the implementation of the new HCV practice protocol and guidelines. The receptionist checked patients in and attach a new patients' referral form to the patients' chart. Medical assistants (MAs) roomed the patients and obtained their vital signs as well as medical and social history. Then, they placed a yellow sticker on the front of the chart and clipped a flow chart, a checklist, and a medication list on the left-hand side of the patients' chart to cue providers to further screen and treat for HCV if the patient met the protocol criteria. The MD and TL followed CPGs for screening and treatment for HCV as a guide. Working remotely, IT staff and financial services personnel helped the project team gather patient demographic information and the ICD-10 billing code (disease diagnosis code) used for this project. Team members' understanding of the process was informally assessed during face-to-face biweekly team meetings. The TL used a data collection tool (Table 6) to track the number of patients flagged by MAs and screened, diagnosed, and treated by the

providers. The TL collected the data every two weeks for three months post-implementation of the CPGs.

Study. The third stage involves identifying whether improvement occurred after change implementation or if further improvement is needed (Crowfoot & Prasad, 2017). This phase included assessing the data collected during the second phase via chart review. The data was plotted by using various data visualization tools in the QI Macros software program, such as a “run” chart over time to evaluate the change and its effectiveness. The TL evaluated the effectiveness of the implementation by measuring the number of charts flagged, the number of patients screened, and the number of patients treated. Those findings were then discussed with the rest of the team to determine improvement or lack thereof.

Act. ‘During the last phase of the PDSA cycle, the team evaluated the effectiveness of the implementation of a new clinic screening protocol for HCV patients and determined whether meaningful improvement took place. If the team is satisfied with the changes, the TL will facilitate the full implementation and adaptation of the new screening protocol. The TL will continue participating in a regular biweekly office meeting to educate and inform office staff on any changes on HCV CPGs even after the full implementation of the new protocol. Additionally, the TL will screen patients’ charts to maintain consistent use of evidence-based CPGs for HCV patients.

Figure 1. PDSA Model. A modified version of the PDSA model courtesy of W. Edwards Deming, 1993.

Plan for Literature Review

To complete this quality improvement project of implementing and evaluating EBP guidelines for HCV screening and treatment in an outpatient GI clinic, the following electronic databases were systematically searched for articles relevant to this topic: CINAHL, PubMed, and Google Scholar. The following search terms were used: hepatitis C screening and treatment, hepatitis C guidelines, provider and patient relationship, provider and collaboration, providers, adherence and compliance, hepatitis C and barriers, and current hepatitis C guidelines. Articles' lists of references were scanned for other relevant articles to augment the earlier findings.

Inclusion criteria for articles were that they be peer-reviewed, written in the English language, published between 2013 and 2019, concerned adults of any gender, and were published in the U.S. Exclusion criteria were the targeting of pregnant women and patients under 18 years of age and published before 2013. The project site serves patients of all genders but does not provide HCV treatment to pregnant females or patients under age 18. Hence, these individuals will be excluded from this project. Studies before the year 2013 will be excluded as they may not be pertinent to current practice guidelines. Studies conducted outside the U.S. will be excluded, as guidelines for HCV screening and treatment may be different in other countries. Articles published in languages other than English will also be excluded as it is not within the scope of this DNP project to translate articles into English. Guidelines for HCV screening and treatment from the CDC, USPSTF, AGA, and AASLD were used as a reference for this project, as they provide relevant data and current practice topics relating to HCV screening and treatment.

Table of Evidence for Literature Review

Table 1

Initial Search Strategy

Topic	Search Terms	Search Terms Combinations	Database EBSCO host plus CINHAL	PubMed	Google Scholar	Total Number
Hepatitis C	Providers	Providers and collaboration	8	13	14,000	21
	Patient relationship	Patient and providers relationship	2	7	17,100	9
	Nurse Practitioner (NP)	Hepatitis C and treatment and NP	6	5	10,300	11
	Treatment Guidelines	Treatment and Guidelines	10	194	37,700	204
	Hepatitis C	guidelines and adherence, compliance	7	13	12,600	20
		Guidelines and adherence and providers	7	9	13,400	16
USPSTF (United States Preventive Services Task Force, 2019) website	https://www.uspreventiveservicestaskforce.org	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
CDC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2019) website	https://www.cdc.gov	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
AGA (American Gastroenterology Association, 2019) website	https://gastro.org	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
AASLD (American Association for the Study of Liver Disease, 2018)		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

LITERATURE REVIEW

Complications of untreated HCV infection can lead to liver failure and cancer, heart problems, muscle and joint pain, kidney dysfunction, depression, and or death (CDC, 2018; Gardenier & Olson, 2019; Moore et al., 2018). This infection is the primary cause of liver transplants in the U.S. (CDC, 2019a). According to the CDC (2019a), acute cases of HCV tripled between 2011 and 2016, from 16,500 to 41,200, due to the increase in IV drug use associated with opioid abuse (CDC, 2019a; DHHS, 2019; Dieterich et al., 2019; Gardenier & Olson, 2019; Guss et al., 2018).

Literature suggests that people in correctional facilities, veterans, experiencing homelessness, those who are pregnant, and those living with HIV are at high risk for HCV infection (CDC, 2019b; Feldman, Balise, Schiff, Whitehead, & Thomas, 2017; Moore et al., 2018; Department of Veterans Affairs [VA], 2019). The current HCV prevalence report published by the CDC (2019a) states that approximately 2.4 million Americans are living with chronic HCV. The National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey analyzed blood test results between 2013 and 2016 and found that 1% of the adult population was living with HCV infection (CDC, 2019a; Rosenberg et al., 2018). This study further found that HCV prevalence differed by state. The nine Western states (California, Texas, Florida, New York, Pennsylvania, Ohio, Michigan, Tennessee, and North Carolina) accounted for 51.9% of all HCV-infected persons compared to the other states (Rosenberg et al., 2018). The study concluded that the nine Western states experienced a higher prevalence of HCV between 2013 and 2016 due to the opioid crisis

and IV drug use during that period (Hofmeister et al., 2019; Rosenberg et al., 2018). In 2018, the CDC reported 2,967 acute cases of HCV infections nationwide.

Literature indicates that chronically infected individuals can remain asymptomatic for years after they contract the disease and may not be aware of their infectious status (CDC, 2019a; Dieterich et al., 2018; Feldman et al., 2017). Feldman et al. (2017) found that 43% to 74% out of 2.7 to 3.9 million people in the U.S. are estimated to have undiagnosed HCV infection, similar to the data presented by Lebovics et al. (2017). Hence, the literature shows the need for providers to address the issue by screening, diagnosing, and treating at-risk patients to combat the rising problem of HCV infection.

Screening and Diagnosis of HCV

HCV Screening

Timely screening and treatment for HCV can help avoid liver disease and its complications. According to the current clinical guidelines (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC 2019; USPSTF, 2019), routinely screening high-risk individuals will be the first step in identifying HCV-infected patients. High-risk individuals are those born between 1945 and 1965, IV drug users, individuals receiving blood or organ transfusion before 1992, individuals born to an HCV-infected mother, individuals with HIV infection, pregnant women, men who have sex with men, individuals with multiple sex partners, individuals with tattoos and body piercings, and prisoners (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC 2019b; USPSTF, 2019). Additionally, a brief screening of individuals' HAV and HBV immunization status, their previous HCV treatment history, and screening for

alcohol and drug use is strongly recommended in the current CPGs (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC, 2019b; USPSTF, 2019).

Alcohol and drug use are known to have a negative effect on liver health and disease advancement (CDC, 2019a; Shiffman, 2018). Literature suggests that individuals with a history of alcohol and drug abuse are more likely to engage in high-risk behaviors, increasing their chance of HCV and other viral hepatitis reinfections (Barua et al., 2015; Grebely et al., 2015; NIDA, 2019). Also, individuals who use alcohol and drugs are more likely to have low treatment adherence (National Institute on Drug Abuse [NIDA], 2019; Novo-Veleiro et al., 2016; Shiffman, 2018). Hence, it is important for healthcare providers to screen and counsel HCV patients to avoid alcohol intake before and during the treatment (Shiffman, 2018; Novo-Veleiro et al., 2016). Once individuals at risk are screened, the HCV antibody blood test is recommended to confirm their diagnosis.

HCV Diagnosis

The current CPGs recommend that an individual with positive antibodies be tested for HCV RNA (ribonucleic acid) level to check for the presence of chronic HCV infection (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC, 2019b; Gardenier & Olson, 2019; USPSTF, 2019). They also recommend a complete metabolic panel as well as tests for complete blood count, alfafeto protein, liver damage, HBV and HIV antibodies, pregnancy if applicable, and for the presence of alcohol and drugs (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC, 2019b; USPSTF, 2019). Before starting the patient on HCV treatment, it is recommended that ultrasound, MRI of the liver, and/or liver biopsy be obtained based on the individual case and disease advancement to assess liver health (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; Gardenier et al., 2015). It is essential to check the diagnosed individual for genotypes due

to specific treatment and duration requirements (Dieterich et al., 2019; Gardenier & Olson, 2019; Guss et al., 2018).

Genotypes and Treatment for HCV

Genotypes (GTs) are genetically distinct viruses that require a specific treatment approach, and HCV is comprised of six GTs: 1a & b, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 (CDC, 2019b; Guss et al., 2018). Approximately 75% of Americans with HCV are infected with genotype 1 (subtypes 1a or 1b), 20% to 25% with genotypes 2 or 3, and a small percentage with 4, 5, or 6 (Gardenier & Olson, 2019; Guss et al., 2018; VA, 2019). In recent years, HCV treatment efficacy has improved the SVR rate to 97% from between 15% and 29% (Dieterich et al., 2019; Guss et al., 2018; Lebovics et al., 2017). The SVR rate is defined as the absence of HCV in the blood serum after completion of antiviral treatment and is considered a measure of HCV treatment success (Terrault & Hassanein, 2016).

Traditionally, HCV treatment (Interferon Alpha-based monotherapy) was recommended for 48 weeks and resulted in an SVR rate of 15% to 20% (Lebovics et al., 2017). Ribavirin with Alpha Interferon, approved for 24 to 48 weeks in 1998, increased the response rate to between 31% and 38% (Guss et al., 2018). Between 2000 and 2001, the FDA approved Pegylated Interferon and Ribavirin, which had SVR rates of 40% to 56% (Olson, Gardenier, & Jacobson, 2015). In 2003, a Protease Inhibitor, Nucleotide Polymerase Inhibitor, and a Sofosbuvir were approved for GT1 HCV. The combination of Sofosbuvir and Ribavirin for HCV GT 2 and 3 and Sofosbuvir with Pegylated

Interferon with Ribavirin for GT 4 was approved around the same time (Olson et al., 2015).

In 2011, the Direct-Acting Antiviral (DAA) was approved for GT 1 and had an SVR rate of 68% to 75% (Olson et al., 2015; Terrault & Hassanein, 2016). DAA is a medication developed to target a particular viral structure and interrupt the viral replication process (Chhatwal et al., 2016; Dieterich et al., 2019; Guss et al., 2018). In 2014, another form of DAA, called Harvoni (Ledipasvir/Sofosbuvir), was approved for GT 1 for 12 weeks (Olson et al., 2015; Terrault & Hassanein, 2016).

Three pan-genotypic (suitable for all genotypes of HCV) therapies have been approved since 2016, with an SVR rate of 97% for 8 or 12 weeks (Alleman, 2017). They include Sofosbuvir/Velpatasvir, Glecaprevir/Pibrentasvir, and Sofosbuvir/Velpatasvir/Voxilaprevir (Alleman, 2017; Lebovics et al., 2017). The goal of HCV treatment is to treat all HCV-positive individuals and prevent complications such as liver cirrhosis and/or cancer. Despite the availability of improved and effective HCV treatment, the literature suggests patients still encounter barriers to treatment and care (Grebely et al., 2013; Rogal et al., 2017; Shehata et al., 2018; Sublette et al., 2017; Younossi et al., 2016).

Barriers to Treatment and Care

Despite the availability of injection-free and well-tolerated HCV therapies, multiple studies suggest there are still common barriers to treatment and care (Grebely et al., 2013; Rogal et al., 2017; Shehata et al., 2018; Sublette et al., 2017; Treloar, Rance, & Backmund, 2013; Younossi et al., 2016). Common barriers are stigma, cost of treatment, health insurance, history of substance abuse disorder, history of treatment nonadherence,

mental health disorders, homelessness, socioeconomic status, transportation, and lack of motivation to start treatment (Rogal et al., 2017; Shehata et al., 2018; Treloar et al., 2013; Younossi et al., 2016). Providers' lack of knowledge regarding current screening and treatment guidelines as well as patients' lack of knowledge about HCV and its transmission were additional barriers to treatment and care addressed in the literature (Chhatwal et al., 2016; Dieterich, 2015; Evon, Golin, Bonner, Grodensky, & Velloza, 2015; Gardenier et al., 2015; Grebely et al., 2013; Grodensky & Velloza, 2015).

Providers Adherence to Guidelines

CPGs play an important role in HCV evaluation and management (AASLD, 2018; Dieterich, 2015; Dieterich et al., 2019). Despite guidelines established by the CDC, USPSTF, AGA, and AASLD, there is limited data regarding providers' adherence to HCV CPGs (Dieterich et al., 2019; Gardenier et al., 2015; Hwang, Thomas, Cheung, & Backus, 2013; Sessoms, Reid, Williams, & Hinton, 2015). This raises a question as to whether there is an issue with providers' adherence to screening and treatment guidelines across settings. Literature indicates the providers' adherence to practice guidelines has been associated with factors such as providers' attitude, knowledge about HCV, current recommendations on screening and treatment guidelines, complex nature of guidelines, and time constraints for patient care (Dieterich 2015; Dieterich et al., 2019; Gardenier & Olson, 2019; Konerman et al., 2017; Shehata et al., 2018; Sublette et al., 2015, 2017). The literature notes time constraints as a barrier for providers offering HCV care (Dieterich 2015; Dieterich et al., 2019; Shehata et al., 2018; Sublette et al., 2015, 2017). Southern et al. (2014) examined physician's adherence to an HCV screening protocol for patients at risk. They found that the amount of time available for patient care affected

providers' guidelines adherence. The authors concluded that overall adherence to the guidelines was low. Ongoing educational sessions and assessment of external factors were recommended to maximize providers' adherence to practice guidelines (Southern et al., 2014).

Tools to Improve Guidelines Adherence

For continuity of care for patients with HCV, providers require evidence-based interventions to deliver effective care for optimal health outcomes. In a primary care physician clinic, an electronic record-keeping system helped providers adhere to recommended screening guidelines for HCV (Konerman et al., 2017; Trinh & Turner, 2018). The authors in this study found that the implementation of this electronic health record system (EHR) prompt, which was used to notify providers, increased HCV screening rates fivefold from 7.6% before implementation to 76% a year after the intervention (Konerman et al., 2017). In addition to the EHR, flow charts and checklists have been used in outpatient and inpatient settings to improve patient care (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2019; CDC, 2019a; WHO, 2019). They are simple tools that providers can use for guidance with step-by-step indications for a systematic and thorough plan of care.

Flowchart

A flow chart is a generic visual diagram used in healthcare for quality improvement (QI) projects that convey a step-by-step sequence to carry out a process from start to finish (Nelson, Batalden, Godfrey, & Lazar, 2011). Using a flow chart requires very little training as the diagram helps the project team to visualize the sequence and team members' roles in the process (AHRQ, 2019). The different

components and directions used in the flow chart can help team members take steps to complete the process (Nelson et al., 2011). The CDC (2019b) and AGA (2019) have used a flow chart with recommended screening and testing sequences for identifying HCV infection. Similarly, a flow chart was used by parents in a behavior management program to help their children suffering from attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (Danforth, 2016). Overall, the implementation of the flow chart helped with child-focus strategies for successful parent training (Danforth, 2016). Hence, the flow chart can be used as an important tool for HCV screening and treatment management to improve patient care.

Checklist

A checklist is also a simple tool widely used in healthcare to improve providers' adherence to CPGs, improve communication and collaboration between providers, and reduce medical errors to improve patients' overall health outcomes (Patel et al., 2014; WHO, 2019). A study by Featherston, Dihigo, and Gilder (2018) in a community health setting used a checklist to improve adherence to screening guidelines on psychiatric agents in pediatric patients and found that the increase in providers' adherence to screening guidelines was statistically significant after implementation of this tool. The WHO (2019) developed a surgical checklist that has been adapted and widely used in multiple surgical settings. A systematic review by Patel et al. (2014) showed that the use of the surgical checklist helped with communication between the surgical team and reduced post-surgical complications by 36%. Therefore, the checklist will be used in this

project to improve communication between providers and staff and to improve patient care.

Medication List

Treatment is recommended for all patients infected with HCV. The approval of pan-genotypic therapies simplified the choice of treatment for providers to successfully treat patients (Dieterich et al., 2019; Guss et al., 2018; Lebovics et al., 2017). The treatment is considered successful when the HCV is not detected in the blood serum after completion of therapy (Dieterich et al., 2019; Terrault & Hassanein, 2016).

A flowchart, checklist, and the medication list for this DNP project will be developed by consulting well-recognized CPGs. Clinical guidelines provided by AASLD (2018), AGA (2019), Boldt et al. (2013), CDC (2019b), and USPSTF (2019) will be used as sources to create a flow chart (Figure 5) for HCV screening and treatment to guide staff and providers. They will also be used to develop an HCV screening and treatment checklist (Figure 6).

Likewise, the commonly used medication lists (Figure 7) at this project site will be developed by consulting AASLD (2018) and Guss et al. (2018). AASLD provides updated evidence-based professional guidelines along with experts' input on new HCV treatment guidelines. The medication lists provided by Guss et al. (2018) coincide with AASLD treatment guidelines and are easy to follow. They are listed with HCV GT, their drug class, and the treatment considerations. The information provided by Guss et al.

(2018) in regard to medication indications can help providers in this clinic to choose and treat HCV-positive patients with appropriate medications achieving treatment success.

Guidelines Driven Interventions

Providers play a crucial role in the management of acute and chronic illnesses. Effective screening and treatment can help reduce illnesses and improve health outcomes in patients with chronic HCV (Konerman et al., 2017; Lebovics et al., 2017; Meyer et al., 2015). A systematic review by Meyer et al. (2015) found that evidenced-based interventions are important to enhance HCV screening, diagnosis, treatment, and continuation of care. A study by Konerman et al. (2017) had results similar to those found in Meyer et al. (2015) that evidence-based interventions can guide providers' adherence to the screening and treatment guidelines. By adhering to EBP guidelines, providers can screen, treat, and prevent HCV-related morbidity and mortality while improving patients' overall health (DHHS, 2019). A positive relationship between providers and patients during and after the treatment is essential for optimal health outcomes (Rogal et al., 2017; Skolnik et al., 2019; Treloar et al., 2013). Providers must have a responsibility to educate patients and the community about HCV infection, its transmission, available treatment options, and possible clinical manifestations, such as liver cirrhosis or cancer (CDC, 2019a; DHHS, 2019; Meyer et al., 2015; WHO, 2019). Overall, evidence-based guidelines for HCV screening and treatment can assist providers to effectively screen and treat patients, maximizing treatment outcomes to improve patients' quality of life and reduce the disease burden of HCV.

Table 2

Database: Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature Search (CINAHL/EBSCO)

Terms	Limits	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Hepatitis C and providers and collaboration	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, adults, nonpregnant, studies only in U.S date: 2013–2019	8	4	4	1
Hepatitis C and providers and patient relationship	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, adults, nonpregnant, studies only in U.S date: 2013–2019	4	2	2	0
Hepatitis C and guidelines	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, adults, nonpregnant, studies only in U.S date: 2013–2019	41	37	4	3
Hepatitis C and guidelines and providers and adherence	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, adults, nonpregnant, studies only in U.S date: 2013–2019	11	8	3	2

Note: Articles are excluded based on titles, duplication, and relevance to the project topic.

Table 3

Database: PubMed

Terms	Limits	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Hepatitis C and providers and collaboration	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, adults, nonpregnant, studies only in U.S date:2013–2019	16	10	6	1
Hepatitis C and patient and provider and relationship	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, adults, nonpregnant, studies only in U.S date:2013–2019	7	4	3	1
Hepatitis C and guidelines	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date:2013–2019, studies only in U.S.	134	129	5	2
Hepatitis C and guidelines and providers and adherence	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, adults, nonpregnant, studies only in U.S date:2013–2019	7	5	2	1

Note: Articles are excluded based on titles, duplication, and relevance to the project topic.

Table 4

Database: Google Scholar

Terms	Limits	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Hepatitis C and providers and collaboration	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, adults, nonpregnant, studies only in U.S date:2013–2019	12,500	12,495	5	0
Hepatitis C and patient and provider and relationship	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, adults, nonpregnant, studies only in U.S date:2013–2019	16,500	16,495	5	1
Hepatitis C and guidelines	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date:2013–2019, studies only in U.S.	76,000	76,000	None	none
Hepatitis C and guidelines and providers and adherence	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, adults, nonpregnant, studies only in U.S date:2013–2019	14,800	14,792	8	1

Note: Articles are excluded based on titles, duplication, and relevance to the project topic.

METHODS

The purpose of this DNP project is was to develop, implement, and evaluate EBP guidelines for screening and treating patients at risk for HCV infection and patients with positive HCV infection in an outpatient GI clinic. The project was aimed at creating a systematic, easy-to-follow practice guideline for providers to improve clinical practice and patients' health outcomes.

Setting

This project took place at a privately-owned outpatient GI clinic in Orange County, California, with an MD (Gastroenterologist), a nurse practitioner as TL, a receptionist, a scheduler, two MAs, two IT specialists, and four financial services employees. This clinic served patients with GI and liver-related diseases such as HAV and HBV, ulcerative colitis, Crohn's, and irritable bowel disease. The clinic served approximately 45 to 48 patients in half a day between two providers averaging about 136 patients per week (three half days per week) with an approximate total of 7,000 patients per year and approximately 121 HCV patients per year.

Participants

Participants for this project included one MD, one nurse practitioner as TL, a receptionist, an appointment scheduler, two MAs, two IT specialists, and four financial services employees. The participants played an essential role in the success of this QI project as a project team. Each team member had an assigned role they performed regularly to help run the clinic smoothly and for better patient care. For example, front desk staff checked patients in for their appointments, and MAs obtained patients' health and medical history to help the MD or NP further screen, diagnose, and treat patients.

The IT specialists and financial services personnel helped with the ICD-10 coding and billings claims. Therefore, these participants and their specific roles were vital to the overall success of this project.

Ethical Considerations

Before starting this QI project, approval from the institutional review board (IRB) was requested from California State University, Fullerton. The DNP student obtained a permission letter to carry out this project at the GI clinic. There were no identifiable patient data or information gathered as a part of this project.

Design

The four stages of the PDSA cycle were used as a guide for this QI project. The project involved forming a project team, implementation of an intervention, post-intervention data collection, and evaluation.

Four recognized professional organizations' guidelines were used as a reference to develop and implement EBP guidelines for HCV screening and treatment (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC, 2019b; USPSTF, 2019). There was significant agreement among these guidelines, and major areas were covered.

Plan

Before the QI project was implemented, the TL engaged and collaborated with the project team. During the 30-minute initial educational session, the TL provided an educational in-service to the project team regarding existing best practices and evidence-based guidelines for HCV screening (AASLD; 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC, 2019b; USPSTF, 2019). The TL provided refreshments to the project team during the first educational meeting as an incentive for their time. The flow map, checklist, and a

medication list developed to meet the specific needs of this clinic by consulting the CDC (2019b), AGA (2019), USPSTF (2019), and AASLD (2018) guidelines were made available to the team. A notice with the definition of risk factors for HCV patients was posted on the bulletin board in the front office area where the receptionist and MAs are usually seated. The process, the use of these tools, and team members' particular roles were discussed thoroughly with the project team. As the IT specialists worked off-site, they were contacted by the TL via phone and received an overview of the project and plan. Additionally, the TL contacted them via phone or email when needing their assistance during the project. After the first meeting, the TL held additional project update meetings every two weeks to assess the continuity of the implementation process for three months post-implementation of the new protocol. This meeting allowed both the TL and the project team with an opportunity to discuss the newly implemented CPGs and the process. The potential timelines for this project were outlined so that the progress of the project could be tracked. Additionally, the TL collaborated with the IT specialists and financial services personnel to gather descriptive data on the average number of patients served at the clinic annually and the number of HCV-positive patients for the fiscal year and during the project implementation.

Operational definitions. An operational definition is a clear and concise description of measures that are used during data collection (Grove, Gary, & Burns, 2015). The following operational definitions were used for this DNP project: High-risk patients, HCV+ Antibody (HCV Ab), and HCV+ RNA. High-risk patients are patients born between 1945 and 1965, patients with a history of IV drug use, patients who received blood or organs before July 1992, patients born to an HCV-positive mother, and

patients with positive HIV infection and tattoos and/or piercings. Professional organizations such as AASLD (2018), AGA (2019), CDC (2019b), USPSTF (2019), and WHO (2019) defined the high-risk patient as above. Similarly, Lynch and Wu (2016) and Younossi et al. (2016) have consistently defined high-risk patients in accordance with AASLD, CDC, USPSTF, and WHO recommendations.

Additionally, HCV+ Antibody (HCV Ab) is defined as the presence of HCV AB in the bloodstream, and HCV+ RNA is defined as a quantitative measurement of HCV virus (viral count/presence of the virus) in the bloodstream (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; Boldt et al., 2013; CDC, 2019b; Chhatwal et al., 2016; Dieterich et al., 2019; Guss et al., 2018; Meyer et al., 2015; Younossi et al., 2016). These variables were used for this project by the project team. The TL also used these variables to maintain consistency during data collection.

The TL screened charts (RCR) based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria were patient age of at least 18, HCV+ AB, HCV+ RNA (ribonucleic acid), and the presence of risk factors. The inclusion criteria were used, as they are were recommended by the professional organizations for HCV screening (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC, 2019b; USPSTF, 2019; WHO, 2019). The exclusion criteria for the RCR were pregnancy, HIV/HBV coinfection, and HCV treatment contraindications. The exclusion criteria were used because this clinic did not serve pregnant women, patients with HIV/HBV coinfection, and patients with treatment contraindications such as an allergic reaction to HCV medications. For this QI project, the implementation of the new HCV screening and treatment protocol was expected to take place from September 2019 through December 2019, but the timeframe was subject to change.

Do

Implementation of the new protocol started when the patient checked in with the receptionist at the front desk. The receptionist then confirmed the appointment on the electronic medical records and attached a referral form, received by this clinic from the patients' referring doctor to the patients' chart. Then, the MA assigned to the patient took the patient to the exam room and obtained the patients' vital signs along with their medical and social history. During intake, if the MA identified the patient as HCV+ or at risk for HCV, the MA then flagged the patient's chart by placing a yellow sticker on the front of the chart to prompt the healthcare provider.

Additionally, the MA clipped a flow chart, a checklist, and a medication list on the left-hand side of the patients' chart to cue the MD and TL to follow the new EBP screening and treatment guidelines. The MD and the TL followed the new protocol. Once the patient was served, the patient was discharged from the office by the front desk staff with future instruction and follow-up appointments if needed based on providers' instructions.

The front desk staff and MAs tracked the number of patients flagged on a paper template (Table 7), which were developed and provided by the TL after consulting information from the CDC (2019b), USPSTF (2019), and WHO (2019). Data were collected by the TL (Table 6) every two weeks post-implementation of the CPGs for three months. The data were then logged into the software program called Microsoft Excel 2016 in the DNP student's personal computer, which was secured with a password, and only the TL had access to that computer.

Study

During this phase, the TL screened the list of patients recorded by the MAs on the template provided by the TL every two weeks and collected data using the data collection tool. The outcome measures for the evaluation were the number of patients screened, the number of charts flagged, and the number of patients treated. The data were then used to evaluate the change and its effectiveness and were plotted on a control chart by using a computer software program called QI Macros. A control chart is a simple and easy visual graphic chart used in QI projects in health care. This chart will display the plotted data in a visual representation of process performance and can help determine whether change or improvement is taking place (Provost & Murray, 2011). The findings were discussed with the project team to analyze whether improvement occurred.

Act

The TL discussed the findings and outcomes with the project team. The project team then evaluated the effectiveness of the implementation of the screening protocol and determined whether the meaningful improvement was identified. If the team were satisfied with the changes, the TL would facilitate the full implementation and adaptation of the new HCV screening protocol in the clinic. If the project team were not satisfied with the clinical outcome, then the TL would reassess the process of implementation and start with a new PDSA cycle. Additionally, the TL participated in biweekly office meetings. This allowed the TL to educate staff on changes to the new HCV CPGs and to screen patients' charts to maintain consistent use of evidence-based CPGs.

Data Collection

The TL developed a data collection tool by consulting AASLD (2018), AGA (2019), CDC (2019b), USPSTF (2019), and WHO (2019). All patients' charts flagged by the MAs were reviewed. The descriptive data were collected every two weeks for approximately three months post-implementation of the CPGs.

Measures

All clinic patients were assessed for risk for HCV. Demographic information was gathered as categorical data. The following three measures were calculated:

$$\text{Process Measure 1} = \frac{\text{Total number of patients with HCV risk factors}}{\text{Total number of patients seen in the clinic}}$$

$$\text{Process Measure 2} = \frac{\text{Total number of patients charts flagged}}{\text{Total number of at-risk patients for HCV}}$$

$$\text{Outcome Measure} = \frac{\text{Total number of patients screened with lab}}{\text{Total number of patients with HCV risk factors}}$$

Analysis/Evaluation

All data were entered in QI Macros and were used to plot a control chart that displayed aspects of process performance outcomes. Improvement in the practice post-implementation of CPGs was identified through p Charts (control chart). The project team continued to observe and analyze areas needing improvement.

Expected outcomes. The expected outcome after the completion of this QI project was to develop a simple, evidence-based protocol to improve care for HCV patients. The implementation of this new protocol was also intended to improve communication between providers and staff and to provide consistency of care for patients to improve their overall health and quality of life. Easy access to a guide for providers on CPGs was anticipated to improve providers' adherence to the new protocol, to improve communication and collaboration between providers and staff, and to translate

evidence-based findings into the clinical setting. These are essential components of improving the quality of care and overall patients' health outcomes.

RESULTS

This section is used to discuss this QI project's findings. The purpose of the project was to develop, implement, and evaluate EBP guidelines for screening and treatment of patients at risk for or with HCV in an outpatient GI clinic, which lacked a standardized protocol before project implementation. The newly developed guidelines were implemented for 12 weeks from October 1, 2019, through December 20, 2019. In order to evaluate project effectiveness, data were collected during TL clinic office hours (Mondays, Tuesdays, Thursdays, and Fridays) using a data collection tool developed by the team. The data were tracked and trended biweekly and then analyzed using QI Macros.

During the 12-week project implementation period, all patients presenting to the clinic were screened each day using the developed screening protocol. Among patient charts flagged by front desk staff and MAs using initial screening protocols, patients who screened at high risk for HCV were alerted to providers for further testing and evaluation. A total of 1178 patients were seen in the clinic between the two providers during the project implementation period. Out of 1178 (100%) patients screened for HCV+ or risk for HCV, 701 (59.5%) patients were found to have at least one HCV risk factor (patients born between 1945 and 1965, patients with a past or current history of IV drug use, patients with a history of blood transfusion before 1992, patients born to an HCV-positive

mother, and patients with positive HIV infection, multiple sex partners, MSM, and presence of tattoos and/or piercings).

The MAs flagged charts of patients who were identified as having any HCV risk factors. Providers then evaluated and screened all patients whose charts were flagged and provided them with a lab requisition form for further testing for HCV antibody in the blood serum. If the patient was found to be seropositive, then that patient was further tested for HCV-RNA levels before the initiation of treatment. In the process, the TL audited all initial patient charts screened by the MA and found that the MAs had missed 13 patients whose charts should have been flagged, as there were identified HCV risk factors according to the protocol. During the chart review, the TL noticed that these were the patients who already had a diagnosis of +HCV before visiting this clinic or were on HCV treatment before or during the start of this project and, thus, were excluded from the total. Out of 701, a total of 525 (74.9%) agreed to be screened for HCV and were given a lab requisition form. The remaining 176 (25.1%) patients refused to get tested (declined to receive a lab slip) when offered by the providers and received education regarding the importance of blood testing for HCV.

Throughout this process, the team experienced some barriers that prevented the team from screening patients for HCV, even though these patients had risk factors. Some factors were patient insurance coverage for screening (blood test), consent to be screened, patients' low awareness of HCV infection and its complications, negative societal stigma attached to those with HCV, and the presence of family during a clinic visit. Due to the time limit in this project, the TL was not able to obtain the specific final count of blood results (HCV positive or negative) of patients with risk factors who received a lab

requisition form. However, at the end of this project, out of 525 patients who received a lab slip, 257 patients' lab results were obtained by the providers. Surprisingly, all the lab results received by the providers were negative for HCV (absence of HCV antibody in the blood serum). The providers will continue to monitor lab results of those patients whose results are yet to be obtained, as this information is crucial to providing appropriate patient care. Currently, a total of 27 patients with positive HCV are being monitored using the new HCV protocol. These are the HCV+ patients who had just finished HCV treatment, were halfway through the treatment course, or were just started on the treatment before the starting of this QI project. These patients need ongoing evaluation during and after the treatment to prevent any complications. Hence, they are being monitored regularly, and their labs, radiology, and follow-up appointments are managed using the new protocol for their successful HCV treatment outcomes.

PDSA Cycles

In this QI project, a total of three PDSA cycles (interventions) were completed to implement and evaluate the EBP guidelines to improve screening and treatment in patients with HCV or at risk for HCV infection to improve overall patients care. These cycles are discussed below.

PDSA Cycle 1. The first intervention before the implementation consisted of offering educational sessions by the TL and holding periodic weekly meetings with the project team. During these meetings, each team member's specific role, estimated anticipated timelines, and project updates were discussed. There was no pre-implementation data available to use as a baseline comparison because of the absence of established clinical practice guidelines at this project site. Therefore, to evaluate and track

improvement, the Week 1 (57%) data point was used as a baseline. Every two weeks, the TL plotted the data on a spreadsheet and evaluated the progress of the implementation process on charts using QI Macros. During the evaluation of these data points and trends, the TL noticed that implementation of new HCV screening and treatment protocols was satisfactory across two weeks for both patient screening and chart flagging (Figure 2 and 3). However, then improvement started declining after Week 3 from 52% to 41% and trended similarly for a few weeks after that, followed by a slight increase to 49% (Figure 2), which was unsatisfactory and indicated a potential barrier to implementation. The TL then intervened at Week 6 to explore potential barriers causing declines, which lead to PDSA Cycle 2.

Figure 2. All patients coming to the clinic screened for HCV risk factors using the new HCV protocol for 12 weeks.

PDSA Cycle 2. At week 6, the TL held a meeting with the project team to discuss the findings of the project (five weeks' data for both screening patients and flagging charts). The intervention for this cycle included providing team re-education by the TL regarding the HCV screening and treatment protocol and reviewing charts of patients with risk factors. During the discussion, the MAs revealed that patients referred by the PCP with diagnosed positive HCV and patients already on treatment were not flagged at the initial screening by the MAs. After receiving feedback from the project team, the TL then revised the protocol and process, highlighting the importance of flagging patients' charts who were HCV+ and or at risk for HCV. The TL continued with biweekly meetings with the team and posted reminder notices at the desks of the receptionist and the MAs to further remind staff of the protocol's steps.

Additionally, the team added questionnaires relating to HCV risk factors to the intake forms (in both the English and Spanish versions as most patients presenting to this clinic are usually Spanish speaking), which are filled out by new patients. These forms were used by MAs and providers to further screen patients for HCV risk factors. Hence, the postintervention data after Week 6 demonstrated improvement and a special cause variation with 8 points above the centerline, indicating an increase in HCV screening and chart flagging rates from an average of 63% to an average of 71% for screening (Figure 2) and from an average of 48% to 69% for flagging (Figure 3). This upward trend of data points satisfied one of the rules of a special cause variation, which was a change (shift) in the process of a QI project, so the control chart was modified to show this process change with the new average of 71% (Figure 2 Figure 3).

Figure 3. Patients charts flagged by MAs with HCV risk factors.

PDSA Cycle 3. The third PDSA cycle focused on reinforcing the improvement of the project. Biweekly meetings, positive feedback, and sharing of tracked data (visual graph of progress) motivated the project team to reinforce the improvement process. This progress was evident when the percentage of patients screened for HCV, flagging off a patient's chart with HCV risk factors, and the rates of patients agreeing to a blood test increased simultaneously. More importantly, further improvements and changes were noticed with the second intervention (PDSA cycle 2), such as biweekly meetings, ongoing staff and patient teaching, positive feedback received, and multiple reminders reinforcing project improvement from 63% to 71%.

The data points following Week 11 show promise in trending towards another special cause variation after implementation of PDSA 3. However, there are not enough

data points (only 5 of 8 needed) to claim this change. Figure 4 shows a similar special cause variation in patients agreeing to have their blood tested from an average of 65% (Week 6), with a special cause variation and average change to 88% after PDSA 3 (Figure 4). The overall data showed a significant change in the postimplementation of a new clinical practice guideline of HCV screening.

Overall, at the end of project implementation, the rates of HCV screening increased from an average of 50% to 71%, with the promise of an average of more than 80% beyond Week 12. The clinic was able to provide HCV screening lab tests to 74.9% ($n= 525$) of patients with HCV risk factors ($N= 701$), and 49% ($n= 257$) of patients diagnostic HCV results demonstrating project effectiveness given there were no HCV screening and treatment guidelines at this clinic prior to project inception despite serving a patient population at high risk for HCV. Additionally, the project team provided crucial anecdotal feedback during biweekly team meetings regarding the increase of their and patients' awareness and knowledge of HCV disease, risk factors, transmission, and complications. Hence, the team expressed their satisfaction with project outcomes and have approved the continued use of this newly implemented HCV screening and treatment protocol to improve HCV patient care.

Figure 4. Patients agreeing to get a blood test for HCV with HCV risk factors.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this QI pilot project was to implement EBP guidelines in an outpatient clinic to effectively screen and treat patients who are at risk for or have HCV infection. Currently, the research supports the role of providers in timely screening and treating HCV positive patients to reduce disease transmission, mortality, and morbidity related to HCV (CDC, 2018; Chung et al., 2018; Dieterich et al., 2019; Guss, Sherigar, Rosen, & Mohanty, 2018; Kasting et al., 2018; Southern et al., 2014). Though surprising and meaningful results were observed, multiple barriers were also encountered during this QI project by providers (project team) and patients. These barriers included provider and patient lack of knowledge and awareness about HCV, patients' health insurance coverage, lack of time (for both providers and patients), hesitancy to consent for testing due to the presence of family members in the exam room, and social stigma attached with HCV infection expressed during office visits with providers. Similarly, barriers to HCV screening and treatment were discussed in the literature by Grebely et al. (2013). Lack of time was a similar common barrier reported by patients throughout project implementation. Several patients expressed that time was the concern for their refusal to receive a lab requisition form by providers for diagnostic HCV blood tests. Likewise, time was one of the common obstacles previously reported in the literature by Southern et al. (2014).

The presence of family members in the examination room was also an additional barrier identified during this project, which caused some patients to refrain from being screened for HCV. The negative social stigma attached to HCV and IV drug use (opioid) as well as high-risk behaviors (e.g., incarceration) were reasons expressed by providers

during team meetings for patients' hesitancy in agreeing to receive screening for HCV with family present in the exam room. Shehata et al. (2018) stressed societal stigma as one of the barriers that prevented patients from seeking HCV treatment and care. In this QI project, a total of 74.9% ($n= 525$) of patients with HCV risk factors agreed to be screened (received a lab requisition form), whereas about 25.1% ($n= 176$) refused to be tested (declined a lab requisition form). Similarly, Trinh and Turner (2018) reported that 40% of patients declined to be screened when offered by the providers in their QI study. The HCV status of those patients who declined lab testing was unknown. Additionally, HCV status on those patients who already had a lab requisition form but were still waiting to get their labs done before their next office visit was indefinite (meaning some can be HCV positive and some can be negative). However, providers will continue to evaluate outstanding incoming patients' lab results to provide patients with suitable care based on the newly adopted HCV protocol.

The findings from this project provided further evidence that multiple factors prevent providers from efficiently screening their patients for HCV infection regardless of the care setting. Hence, this project addressed the need for further quality improvement studies and the team to continue evaluating project effectiveness in the future. Given project findings, at the end of project implementation and analysis phases, the project team decided to fully adopt and continue the new standardized protocol for this clinic while continuing to monitor effectiveness.

Limitations

This QI project had several limitations, including the size of the clinic, the number of providers, staff, patients' individual motivation to receive screening and

treatment, lack of staff and patient awareness of HCV infection, and the duration of the project. The project site was an outpatient GI clinic with only two providers, two MAs, and a front desk receptionist. This clinic had no previously established standardization of HCV screening and treatment protocols in place. Hence, the process of the new protocol implementation was time-consuming as it required the project team to follow the steps on the flow chart from start to finish (Figure 5) for every patient who met the screening protocol. During the implementation of this project, the project team required multiple educational and training sessions (meetings) to help increase their knowledge and awareness of HCV risk factors, its transmission process, possible complications, and the treatment options available for HCV positive patients. This screening process also required substantial patient education to educate them on the benefits of being screened. The implementation of the new protocol took additional time to follow the process thoroughly, thus reducing the total number of patients seen for the day and adversely affecting the clinic's revenue based on patient quantity. The duration of the project was another limitation, as it required more time to gather data. The process of successful HCV screening and treatment depends on multiple factors such as providers' and patients' time, patients' insurance coverage and their motivation to receive a blood draw, and providers receiving the lab results back for a diagnosis. Due to the limited project time of 12 weeks duration, the exact number of patients' final diagnostic lab status was not available at the end of the project. However, the project team is continuing to monitor outcomes of the blood results and the use of the newly implemented HCV protocol ongoing despite the completion of this QI DNP project. Additionally, because this project was carried out in a small outpatient clinic, the above data cannot be generalized to a larger organization or

larger clinic. Nevertheless, learnings from this project can be used to inform similar future QI projects focusing on implementing new practice guidelines for HCV screening in similar small clinics.

Implication for Practice

The use of the PDSA model was effective in driving new evidence-based practice change to implement new clinical practice guidelines, empowering providers and staff in an outpatient clinic, leading to increased screening, diagnosis, and treatment of HCV positive patients. Findings support adopting the piloted EBP guidelines and ongoing evaluation of its effectiveness through the team approach using the PDSA framework. Future recommendations for practice include the need for providers to assess barriers to an effective HCV screening and treatment process. Examples of some interventions include education for providers and patients and their families on HCV screening and treatment and assisting patients in navigating insurance systems and community resources. A focused educational intervention discussing the benefits of screening and treatment of HCV infection should be provided to patients who refuse initial screening. Providers should encourage patients to make a follow-up appointment so that they have an additional opportunity to receive screening. The published CPG recommended screening everyone born between 1945 and 1965 as they were considered to be at risk for HCV infection (CDC, 2019; Kasting et al., Moore et al., WHO, 2019). Most baby boomers who came for the colon screening in this clinic were screened for HCV as they were considered at risk for HCV because of the year in which they were born. Furthermore, the findings of this QI project showed that the prevalence of HCV was low in the baby boomer's generation in the areas near Anaheim, California, where the project

was implemented. However, more research is needed in the field of screening with this age group to further generalize the findings from this QI project.

Conclusions

In conclusion, many factors may have affected the process of this QI project. Before the implementation of this project, the office staff had minimal knowledge of HCV infection, its transmission, complications, and the importance of the need to implement this new protocol for better and optimal patient care. Other challenges were high patient volume and few providers and MAs. The additional time needed to screen patients by providers and MAs to complete the process was a significant barrier reported by project team members. However, there were several overall project successes, as an improvement was seen regarding HCV screening for patients who were flagged as at risk in a clinic that did not have practice guidelines in place prior to this project. The implementation of this project provided an opportunity for providers to enhance their knowledge of current EBP guidelines on HCV screening and treatment. This project indicated that organizational and team support is critical in any type of QI project and its outcomes. Additionally, this project allowed providers to offer education to office staff and patients regarding HCV risk factors, its transmission, prevention, and the treatment options that are currently available. The results from this project overall showed that engagement in EBP helps providers screen patients efficiently, improving patients' health outcomes, and ultimately enhancing their quality of life.

Table 5

Estimated Timeline Subject to Change

Completion Date	Activities
Plan Phase (August 2019)	Literature review Collaborate with the Medical Director and office staff, including the IT specialist and Financial personnel Initial educational in-service 30 to 40 minutes on current HCV screening and treatment recommendation Seek support and approval to carry out QI project Formation of a project team, assign an individual role
Do Phase (September-December 2019)	Implement the developed CPGs for HCV screening and treatment Meetings with the project team Collect data using a data collection tool every two weeks and plot on the computer softer program to track the progress
Study Phase (January-March 2020)	Study the collected data and Evaluate the effectiveness of the implementation of a new CPG
Act Phase (April-May 2020)	Report findings of the QI project to the project team If satisfied with the outcome, publish a new protocol for the clinic

Note: The above-projected timeline may change depending on the time of the implementation of this project (Do Phase).

Figure 5. Outpatient GI clinic HCV (Hepatitis C) screening and treatment flowchart to guide providers. Adapted and modified from (AASLD, 2018) (AGA, 2019), Boldt et al. (2013), CDC, (2019b) and USPSTF (2019).

CHECKLIST FOR HCV SCREENING AND TREATMENT

Initial HCV Labs Before Treatment (If positive antibody for HCV)

Indicators	Y	N	Indicators	Y	N
____ HCV RNA	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ HAV & HBV vaccine	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
____ HCV GT	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ HIV AB if not available	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
____ CMP	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ Fibrosure level	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
____ CBC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ Abdominal U/S	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
____ HBsAB, HBsAg, HBcAB if all (-) vaccine	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ EGD if cirrhosis for varices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Treatment Start Date	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ Alcohol and Drug toxicology	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Monitoring During Treatment

Week 2 (if on Ribavirin)	Y	N	Week 8, 12, 16 & 24	Y	N
____ CBC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ CBC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
____ CMP	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ CMP	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Week 4			____ AFP	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
____ HCV RNA	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ HCV RNA (at the end of treatment)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
____ CBC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Treatment End Date _____		
____ CMP	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Follow-up	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F/U appointment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			____ Refill Reminder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Monitoring After Treatment

12 weeks after the Treatment	Y	N	Yearly Post Treatment	Y	N
____ CBC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ CBC, CMP & AFP	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
____ CMP	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Advanced Fibrosis (F3): U/S of Abdomen & AFP q 6 months	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
____ HCV RNA (test for cure)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____ Every 2-3 years	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6 months post-treatment If advanced fibrosis or cirrhosis monitor AFP & U/S every 6 months to screen for mass or hepatocellular carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	(Advanced Fibrosis F4): U/S & AFP every 6 months; yearly CBC, CMP, AFP, PT/INR _____	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			____ F/U appointment		

Figure 6. Outpatient GI clinic HCV (Hepatitis C) screening and treatment checklist to guide providers. Adapted and modified from (AASLD, 2018) (AGA, 2019), Boldt et al. (2013), CDC, (2019b), Guss et al. (2017), Dieterich et al. (2019), and USPSTF (2019).

HCV MEDICATION LIST

	Generic name	HCV genotype	Duration	Monitor
Epclusa	Sofosbuvir/Velpatasvir	1-6	12 weeks with & without cirrhosis	CBC, CMP, cannot be used in renal failure
Harvoni	Sofosbuvir/Ledipasvir	1,4,5,6	8 weeks without cirrhosis, 12 weeks with and without cirrhosis	CBC, CMP, cannot be used in renal failure
Mavyret	Glecaprevir/Pibrentasvir	1-6	8 weeks without cirrhosis, 12 weeks with cirrhosis	CBC, CMP, can be used in renal failure
Zepatier	Elbasvir/Grazoprevir	1b,4	12 weeks with & without cirrhosis	CBC, CMP, cannot be used in decompensated (Child B/C)
Ribavirin	Ribavirin	1-6	8 - 12 weeks based on individual patients' case	CBC, CMP anemia

Figure 7. FDA approved medication lists (commonly used medications for HCV-positive patients in this outpatient GI clinic) adapted and modified from AASLD (2018) and Guss et al. (2018).

Table 6

Data Collection Tool for DNP Project (September 2019-December 2019)

Week #	PT ID	Risk factors (HCV)	Charts flagged by MAs	Patients screened by Providers	Patients treated by Providers	Comments
1		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
2		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
3		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
4		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
5		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
6		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
7		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
8		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
9		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
10		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
11		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
12		Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	

Note: High-risk patients for HCV include: a) patients born between 1945 and 1965; b) patients with a history of IV drug use; c) any patients who received blood or organs before 1992; d) patients born to an HCV-positive mother; and e) patient with positive HIV infection and tattooing and piercing (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC; 2019b; USPSTF, 2019; WHO, 2019).

F=female, HCV=hepatitis C virus, ID=identification, M=male, MAs=medical assistants, N=no, PT=patient, Y=yes, #=number.

Table 7

List of Patients Flagged by MAs (September 2019-December 2019)

List of patients	PT ID	Gender M/F	Risk factors (HCV) (a) patients born between 1945 and 1965; (b) patients with a history of IV drug use; (c) any patients who received blood or organs before July 1992; (d) patients born to an HCV-positive mother; and (e) patient with positive HIV infection and tattooing and piercing	Comments

Note: Risk factors for HCV (AASLD, 2018; AGA, 2019; CDC; 2019b; USPSTF, 2019; WHO, 2019).

F=female, HCV=hepatitis C virus, ID=identification, M=male, MAs=medical assistants, PT=patient.

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APPENDIX A

APPROVAL REQUEST

 SOUTHERN CALIFORNIA CSU DNP CONSORTIUM

Gayatri Subedi
 800 N State College Blvd.
 Fullerton, CA 92831

June 10, 2019

Ravindra Alapati, MD
 Digestive & Liver Disease Inc.
 W. Romney Dr.
 Anaheim, CA 92801

Dear Dr. Alapati,

As you are aware that I am currently enrolled in the Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) program at California State University (CSU) Fullerton. As a part of my program, I am required to complete the DNP project/evidence-based practice change in my clinical setting. In evaluating my clinical site, I have identified the need to implement current clinical practice guidelines (CPG) for HCV screening and treatment because of the patient population we encounter and serve regularly. A simplified, easy to follow standard protocol will augment the care for HCV patients and improve communication between providers and staff. The title of my project is "Implementation of HCV Screening and Treatment Guidelines in an Outpatient Clinic."

To successfully conduct and implement this Quality Improvement (QI) project, I would like to request your support and approval. Attached is a detailed project summary for your review. Thank you very much.

Sincerely,

 Gayatri Subedi, NP
 DNP Student
 CSU Fullerton, CA

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium
 Fullerton • Long Beach • Los Angeles

SOUTHERN CALIFORNIA CSU DNP CONSORTIUM

The anticipated time for this Quality Improvement (QI) project is from September 2019-January, 2020, and will involve the following:

1) Developing, implementing and evaluating CPG for screening and treatment of patients at risk for HCV infection and or patient with positive HCV infection (adapted from CDC, AASLD, AGA, and USPSTF).

2) A collaboration of the DNP student (an employee of the project site) with the project team (Medical Director/Doctor, front desk staff, MAs, IT, and financial services personnel) to discuss the QI project (August 2019). A brief education session on current evidence-based CPG, a flow chart, checklist, and a medication list, adapted and modified (AASLD, AGA, CDC, and USPSTF) to meet the specific need of the project site will be discussed with the Medical Doctor and the project team before the project is carried out (September 2019-December 2019). The project team will be assigned to their respective roles. The focus of this QI project will be on improving the care for HCV patients, to increase the efficiency of patient flow, and to enhance communication between the providers and staff. The data will be collected by the DNP student every two weeks. The TL will hold biweekly meetings for three months post-implementation of the new protocol. The participants (project team) will include: the front desk staff, MAs, MD, NP (TL), and financial services personnel. The IT specialists will be contacted by the DNP student via phone when needing their help and support as they work remotely. This meeting will allow both the TL and the project team with an opportunity to discuss the newly implemented CPG and the process. Additionally, it will allow the TL to provide an education to staff on any changes made on the new HCV CPG, and to screen patients' charts to maintain consistency of the use of evidence-based CPG for HCV patients in this clinical setting.

3) The effectiveness of the project will be evaluated by (DNP student) measuring: how many patients' charts were flagged by front desk staff and MAs when identified at risk for HCV infection or HCV+ patients and patients were screened, and how many patients treated for HCV using the new protocol (flow chart, checklist and the medication list). Data collection will be done by the DNP student every two weeks for three months post-implementation of the CPG.

4) After completion of the QI project and data collection (December 2019), the outcomes of the project will be analyzed and discussed with the project team (January 2020).

The data that I collect for this project will be de-identified and protected to comply with HIPPA (Health Insurance Probability and Accountability Act) regulations. This QI project will also be reviewed and evaluated for approval by the California State University Fullerton IRB (Institutional Review Board). Throughout this project, the project materials will be protected and reviewed by the project chairs and myself. Once the project is completed, this will be presented to the DNP committee.

Thank you very much for your support.

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium
Fullerton • Long Beach • Los Angeles

APPENDIX B**APPROVAL LETTER FROM THE PROJECT SITE****Digestive & Liver Disease Specialists****A Medical Group, Inc**

1771 W Romneya Dr, Suite C

Anaheim, CA 92801

Ph: (714)-758-0403, Fax: (714)-917-0785

Ravindra Alapati, MDDiplomat American Board of Gastroenterology,
& Internal Medicine.Date: July 30th, 2019

To,

Gayatri Subedi
Doctoral of Nursing Practice (DNP) student,
University of Fullerton, CA
800 N. State College Blvd, Fullerton
CA 92831

Subject: Permission for Conducting Quality Improvement Research Project

Dear Mrs. Subedi,

I am pleased to inform that I give you permission in respect of your research request at our clinic for Quality Improvement (QI) project and extract data from the de-identified patients charts regarding implementing Hepatitis C screening and treatment protocols. Your initiative is appreciable, and I am ready to support you with your research project with all my best efforts.

I wish you all the best in your research project.

Best Regards,

Dr. Ravindra Alapati, MD

APPENDIX C

IRB APPROVAL FROM CSU, FULLERTON, CA

irb@fullerton.edu <irb@fullerton.edu>
 To: gsubedi@csu.fullerton.edu, hfraley@fullerton.edu
 Cc: irb@fullerton.edu

Wed, Sep 18, 2019 at 8:32 AM

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects
 P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

From the Institutional Review Board
 California State University, Fullerton

September 18, 2019

From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
 CSUF Institutional Review Board

To: PI: Gayatri Subedi

Application No. HSR-19-20-6
 Study Title: Implementation of Clinical Practice Guidelines

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 4. Secondary research for which consent is not required: Secondary research uses of identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens, if at least one of the following criteria is met:

- (i) The identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens are publicly available;
- (ii) Information, which may include information about biospecimens, is recorded by the investigator in such a manner that the identity of the human subjects cannot readily be ascertained directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects, the investigator does not contact the subjects, and the investigator will not re-identify subjects;
- (iii) The research involves only information collection and analysis involving the investigator's use of identifiable health information when that use is regulated under 45 CFR parts 160 and 164, subparts A and E, for the purposes of "health care operations" or "research" as those terms are defined at 45 CFR 164.501 or for "public health activities and purposes" as described under 45 CFR 164.512(b); or
- (iv) The research is conducted by, or on behalf of, a Federal department or agency using government-generated or government-collected information obtained for nonresearch activities, if the research generates identifiable private information that is or will be maintained on information technology that is subject to and in compliance with section 208(b) of the E-Government Act of 2002, 44 U.S.C. 3501 note, if all of the identifiable private information collected, used, or generated as part of the activity will be maintained in systems of records subject to the Privacy Act of 1974, 5 U.S.C. 552a, and, if applicable, the information used in the research was collected subject to the Paperwork Reduction Act of 1995, 44

U.S.C. 3501 et seq.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposed was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office
Hannah Fraley

APPENDIX D**HCV SCREENING QUESTIONNAIRES FOR PATIENTS (ENGLISH VERSION)**

Digestive & Liver Disease
A Medical Group Inc.
1771 W. Romneya Dr. Suite C
Anaheim, Ca 92801
Phone: 714.758.0403 FAX: 714.917.0785

Ravindra Alapati, MD
Diplomat American Board of Gastroenterology &
Internal Medicine & Liver Disease

Gayatri Subedi, NP
RN BSN MSN FNP-BC

Are you at risk for Hepatitis C (HCV) infection? Does any one of these risk factors apply to you? Please check "yes" or "no" if yes then talk to your provider for Hepatitis C screening :-

- (1) Are you born between 1945 and 1965? Yes / No
- (2) Do you have a history of IV drug use or current use? Yes / No
- (3) Have you received blood or organs before 1992? Yes / No
- (4) Are you born to an HCV-positive mother? Yes / No
- (5) Are you positive for HIV infection? Yes / No
- (6) Do you have multiple sex partners? Yes / No
- (7) Are you a man having sex with the same sex person? Yes / No
- (8) Do you have a history of tattooing and or piercing? Yes / No

Thank you for answering these questions!

APPENDIX E

HCV SCREENING QUESTIONNAIRES FOR PATIENTS (SPANISH VERSION)

Digestive & Liver Disease
A Medical Group Inc.
 1771 W. Romneya Dr. Suite C
 Anaheim, Ca 92801
 Phone: 714.758.0403 FAX: 714.917.0785

Ravindra Alapati, MD
 Diplomate American Board of Gastroenterology &
 Internal Medicine & Liver Disease

Gayatri Subedi, NP
 RN BSN MSN FNP-BC

¿Está en riesgo de contraer la infección de Hepatitis C (HCV)? ¿Algunos de estos factores de riesgo si aplica a usted? Marque "Sí" o "No" en caso afirmativo y luego diríjase a su proveedor para una evaluación de Hepatitis C: -

- (1) |Usted nacio entre el año 1945 – 1965? Si ___ / No ___
- (2) Tiene antecedentes de uso de Drogas intravenosas o uso actual ? Si ___ / No ___
- (3) Has recibido sangre o organos antes de 1992 ? Si ___ / No ___
- (4) Ha nacido de madre positiva al Hepatitis C ? Si ___ / No ___
- (5) Eres positivo al VIH? Si ___ / No ___
- (6) Tiene multiples parejas sexuales? Si ___ / No ___
- (7) Eres un hombre que tiene relacion con el mismo sexo? Si ___ / No ___
- (8) Tiene historial de tatuajes o aretes de multiple cantidad? Si ___ / No ___

Gracias por contestar estas preguntas !